

ALLERGY. CAUSES OF ORIGIN

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ABSTRACT: WHAT IS AN ALLERGY? Allergies are very common. According to health authorities, approximately 20% of people in North America and Western Europe are affected by pollinosis (allergic rhinoconjunctivitis, allergic rhinitis). All over the world, the number of people suffering from allergies is increasing. According to Allergy UK, around 30-40% of people will experience allergies at some point in their lives. Allergies are most common in children, especially food allergies

KEY WORDS: Pollinosis, cough, note, rhinitis, swelling, anaphylaxis, itching, shock, dry skin, diarrhea, bronchospasm.

INTRODUCTION: ALLERGY SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS When an allergic person comes into contact with an allergen, an allergic reaction does not occur immediately. The immune system gradually increases sensitivity to the substance. Over time, the body acquires its own high sensitivity - this process is called sensitization. Sensitization can last from several days to several years. In most cases, the sensitization process is not completed and the patient has some symptoms, but not a full allergic reaction. When the immune system reacts to the allergen, inflammation and irritation appear. Signs and symptoms depend on the type of allergen. Allergic reactions can occur in the intestines (digestive system), skin, sinuses, airways, eyes and nasal passages:

Symptoms of allergy to dust and dust mites have the following symptoms

Runny nose; Itching of the eyes; Itching in the nose; Rhinitis; Swelling of the eyes; Watery eyes; Coughing.

Symptoms of skin allergies, such as eczema (atopic dermatitis):

Skin shedding; Itching; Skin dryness; Red rashes on the skin.

Allergies to food products (food) have different reactions:

Return; Swelling of the tongue; Soreness in the mouth; Swelling of the lip; Swelling of the face; Swelling of the throat; Stomach spasm; Respiratory disorders; Rectal bleeding (rarely in children); Diarrhea;

Anaphylaxis (anaphylactic shock) is a very serious, often life-threatening allergic reaction.

Allergy to insect bites has the following symptoms:

Hoarseness of voice; Swelling of the bite site; A sharp drop in blood pressure; Skin itching; Dizziness; Cough; Difficulty breathing; Anxiety; Anaphylaxis.

Allergy to drugs can have the following symptoms:

Hoarseness of voice; Swelling of the tongue; Swelling of the lip; Swelling of the face; Skin rash; Itching; Symptoms of anaphylactic shock.

MAIN SECTION: SYMPTOMS OF ANAPHYLACTIC SHOCK Anaphylactic shock is a severe allergic reaction with a rapid onset. Anaphylactic shock can be life-threatening and should be treated as a medical emergency. This type of allergic reaction reflects several different symptoms that can appear within minutes of exposure to the allergen. If the allergen directly affects the blood, the onset of an allergic reaction is usually from 5 to 30 minutes. A reaction to a food allergen takes longer. Anaphylaxis requires immediate medical attention.

MANIFESTATION OF ANAPHYLACTIC SHOCK IN THE SKIN AND MUCOUS MEMBRANE

All parts of the body, redness and itching are observed. Damaged tissues also swell (angiodystrophy). Some people may experience a burning sensation on the skin. Swelling of the tongue and throat is observed in about 20% of cases. If the skin has a strange blue color, it can be a sign of hypoxia (lack of oxygen).

Some patients may have a stuffy nose. The mucous membrane covering the front of the eyes and the inside of the eyelids (conjunctiva) can be inflamed.

CHANGES IN BREATHING DURING ANAPHYLAXIS

Difficulty breathing; Whistling during breathing due to spasms of the bronchus; Stridor is a strong trembling sound during breathing; Suffocation of the voice; Odynophagia - pain when swallowing; Coughing;

CARDIOVASCULAR CHANGES

Coronary artery spasm is a sudden (temporary) contraction of the muscle in the artery wall caused by histamine-releasing cells in the heart. This can lead to myocardial infarction, dysrhythmia (abnormal heart rhythm) or heart attack.

Low blood pressure can cause your heart to beat faster. Dizziness occurs due to a sudden drop in arterial blood pressure. Some may lose consciousness. In some cases, low blood pressure may be the only symptom of anaphylaxis.

CHANGES IN THE GASTROINTESTINAL SYSTEM

Abdominal spasm; Diarrhea; Vomiting; Loss of urinary control; Stomach ache.

CAUSES OF ALLERGY DEVELOPMENT

The human immune system responds to an allergen as a pathogen (external harmful substance) and tries to destroy it, like a foreign bacteria, virus, fungus or toxin.

However, the allergen is not harmful. It's just that the immune system has become very sensitive to this substance.

When the immune system reacts to an allergy, it releases immunoglobulin E (IgE), a type of antibody, to destroy the allergen. It produces chemicals in the body that cause an allergic reaction.

One of these chemicals is called histamine. Histamine causes muscle contractions, including those in the walls of blood vessels and airways. Histamine also helps clear mucus from the nose.

An allergy sufferer blames allergy symptoms on an allergen—a friend's pet, plant dust, or dust. However, they are wrong. The problem is not the allergen, but the allergic person's immune system.

RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ALLERGY

In medicine, risk factors are understood as factors that worsen the disease or the patient's condition. This risk can be caused by what a person does. For example, smoking is a risk factor for lung disease.

Below are some of the risk factors associated with allergies:

Having a person with asthma in the family - if your parents, grandparents or great-grandfather had asthma, you also have a risk of developing allergies;

Having a person with allergies in the family - if a close relative is allergic, there is a possibility that you will also develop allergies.

Children have more allergies than adults. On the plus side, many children outgrow their allergies as they get older.

Having asthma - people with asthma are more likely to develop allergies;

Insufficient exposure to sunlight - scientists from the European Center for Environmental Protection and Human Health and researchers from various Australian centers found that children living in areas with little sunlight have a higher rate of developing allergies.

THE MOST WIDELY DISTRIBUTED ALLERGEN

Allergen is a substance that causes an allergic reaction in some sensitive individuals.

ALLERGY TO ANIMALS:

Dust fleas - their excrement; Wool; Fur; Bran; Fel d1 is a protein found in cat's sebaceous and salivary glands;

MEDICAL ALLERGENS

Penicillin; Salicylates are salts of salicylic acid usually found in aspirin; Sulfanamides.

AMONG FOOD PRODUCTS

Oatmeal; Celery; Pumpkin; Bean;

INSECTS

Poisonous insects; Fly; Bees; Ants Flea;

ALLERGY DIAGNOSIS

There are several ways to identify allergies. The doctor asks the patient questions about the origin of the allergy, when it appears, and the symptoms of the allergy. In addition, it is asked if other family members have allergies.

There are a number of tests for allergies. Here are some examples:

A blood test measures the level of IgE antibodies produced by the immune system. This test is sometimes called a radioallergen sorbent test (RAST).

A skin prick test is also known as a test before taking various antibiotics. The skin is scratched with the tip of the syringe, and a little less allergen is applied to this place. If there is a skin reaction - itching, redness and swelling may indicate the presence of an allergy

Patch test is used in patients with dermatitis (eczema). The required amount of suspected allergen was placed on special metal disks and attached to the belt. The doctor checks the skin reaction after 48 hours.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that the origin of allergy can be very different reasons. Their waists are different. Even a single allergen causes severe consequences for people, sometimes breathing difficulties due to bronchospasm can lead to death. Therefore, in the treatment of allergy, the cause that caused it is sought and an attempt is made to eliminate it.

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